

Some features of teaching the Russian language to foreign students of technical universities with an engineering profile

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Abstract: The article discusses some features of teaching the Russian language to foreign audiences at technical universities, pays attention to the selection of material, the choice of reading texts used in practical classes, and characterizes the individual specifics of perception and presentation of the material.

Key words: reading, text, spheres of communication, Russian as a foreign language, types of speech activity, foreign languages.

Modern methods of teaching Russian as a foreign language are focused on teaching foreign speakers not only general mastery of the language, but also mastery of the language of their specialty. Professionally oriented teaching of Russian as a foreign language arose in domestic universities at the beginning of the second half of the 20th century with the appearance of foreign students in universities who came to the country of the language being studied to obtain higher education and profession. In this regard, there is a need for a comprehensive and interconnected formation and development of skills and abilities in all four types of speech activity.

When teaching the language of a specialty, the main task is the development and formation of students' speech skills and abilities in those types, forms and areas of speech communication on which their educational activities are based when mastering special scientific disciplines. Moreover, the student's field of activity influences the nature of this activity and determines its types and forms.

The following areas of activity of foreign non-philological students are distinguished:

1. Educational and scientific sphere: listening to lectures, participating in seminars, making a report at a scientific conference, discussing professional problems, etc.

2. Social and political sphere: reading the press, listening to the radio, watching television programs, using social networks, etc.

3. Social and cultural sphere: visiting theaters, concerts, reading works of art, discussing problems of literature, art, sports, etc.

4. Social sphere: everyday interpersonal communication, communication in the field of catering, consumer services, etc.

5. Administrative and legal sphere: preparation of official documents, etc.

As is known, each sphere of communication requires a certain set of communicative roles, speech genres, forms and styles of communication in the modern Russian language. Thus, in the administrative, legal and educational and scientific spheres, students will need official business and scientific styles of speech; in the social and everyday sphere - conversational speech, the ability to adequately respond to cues, spontaneously answer questions, take part in dialogues on general topics, while avoiding communication failures; in administrative law - possession of certain codes of oral scientific speech, without using elements of a colloquial style of speech, characteristic of everyday, interpersonal communication.

However, it must be taken into account that the communicative needs of foreign students in all areas of speech activity are unequal. For example, speech needs in the administrative and legal sphere are of a rather peripheral nature, and by the time they start studying at universities, foreign speakers already acquire some necessary communication skills in the conditions of the Russian linguistic and cultural community in the social and everyday sphere. Thus, in the learning process, the most important are the communicative needs in the educational, scientific, socio-cultural and socio-political spheres of activity.

The category of non-philology students is very heterogeneous. Their common feature is that the goal of learning a language is to use it in the process of mastering one's main specialty. These are bachelors and masters studying at universities and mastering the language to obtain a specialty and communicate in various fields of activity; graduate students for whom the most relevant areas are professional and socio-political; trainees whose main activity is in the professional field; These are students of foreign universities with a variety of preliminary training in the Russian language, whose main task is communication in the educational and professional sphere, mediated by text (reading) and direct (speaking). There is also a group of foreign specialists for whom the only goal of studying the Russian language is reading specialized literature. It is mandatory for all categories of students to master and master the normative characteristics of the scientific style of speech - the basis of communication in the educational and professional field of activity.

Taking into account the learning objectives of each category of students, educational material is selected and rationally organized. The selection takes into account the genre of texts used by students. Depending on the duration of training, the material may be minimized; What matters is in what types of activities the language will be used, receptive or reproductive.

In the practice of teaching the Russian language to foreign non-philological students, a significant place is occupied by texts of a general scientific and highly specialized nature.

Proof is a method of presentation through which the truth of a person's knowledge about the world, which was in the nature of hypotheses or judgments not verified by practice, is confirmed or denied.

The division itself into philology students and non-philologists is very arbitrary, since the concept of “non-philologists” included economists, biologists, geographers, and students of technical universities. Nowadays there is a tendency towards increasing differentiation of students. Let's focus on teaching students of technical universities.

Engineering students learn on the principle of progressive information processing; they are good at standard language programs, which include questions for assimilation, working with a dictionary, analyzing vocabulary, etc. They willingly study grammar; they first need to explain the rule, then suggest a way to complete the task. They need graphs, models, tables.

When working with lexical units, students at technical universities try to analyze them, memorize lists of lexemes, and use bilingual dictionaries to check the exact meaning of a term.

These students need help developing their speaking and writing fluency. It is also necessary to pay special attention to listening tasks and to developing reading fluency.

Engineering students do best in written assignments and learning activities that allow them to analyze and draw their own conclusions, both individually and in groups.

Although they are usually more accurate in the use of lexemes and the application of rules than in the humanities, students in technical universities usually complete written work more slowly, since they need more time to think about and carefully complete tasks.

Students of technical universities are usually inclined to self-control and have good long-term memory, so the teacher should correct mistakes immediately. As practice shows, this does not confuse their thoughts and helps to implant the correct model in their memory.

However, it is more difficult for students of technical universities to “talk”; they are hampered by excessive control over their own speech. Thus, with productive types of speech activity they usually use pre-learned phrases and texts that they can incorporate into their own spoken utterances without prior thought. Communicative tasks that promote memorization of entire blocks and phrases make it possible to spontaneously use the language of a specialty in speech without rote learning, thereby helping to get rid of too strict self-control over one’s speech.

However, when teaching engineering students, the emphasis should be on written language, since in the scientific and technical genre it is the main one, and the oral type is derivative.

Thus, when teaching a language of specialty in technical universities with an engineering profile, it is necessary to pay special attention to receptive types of speech activity, namely reading as one of the most important and basic, however, it should be noted that the sequence of methodological steps proposed by the teacher involves a transition from mastering a foreign language using language means to the formation of his speech skills and the development of speech skills of both receptive and productive types of speech activity.

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